

CREATING FACILITIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM AND KNOWING HOW TO USE THEM

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Abstract. This article is dedicated to creating facilities in the educational system of the Republic of Uzbekistan and knowing how to use them

Keywords: Educational convenience, why small changes lead to big results, amazing power of single atomic habits, role of skilled professionals in educational system.

Today, all spheres of the life of New Uzbekistan have become a field of deep reforms. In this process, it is impossible not to talk excitedly about the changes in the educational system, which is considered the basis of the social sphere. In recent years, practical work on the organization of all stages of the education system based on modern requirements has entered a decisive stage in our country. As our President noted: "The more educated our children are, the faster the economic sectors based on high technologies will develop, the more social problems will be solved." Therefore, if I say that the threshold of New Uzbekistan starts from the school, I think that our entire nation will support this idea."

During the observations, it should also be emphasized that if we want each young generation to realize our desired goals, we must first be able to arouse enthusiasm, transparency and inquisitiveness in them. The most important thing is to teach the children, who are the representatives of the great future, the level of comfort in the learning process. To what extent are the educational tools and manuals in each classroom, from the table and chair they sit on to the pen they use to write? we should pay attention to comfort.

British author James Clear wrote in his book "Atomic habits: The driving force of small habits" that British cycling changed overnight in 2003. All professional cycling bodies in Great Britain hired Dave Brailsford as head coach. At that time, professional cycling in Great Britain had shown mediocre results for about a hundred years. British cyclists had won only one Olympic victory since 1908. Indeed, the results of British cyclists were so pathetic. One of the largest bicycle manufacturers in Europe refused to sell his products to the British team because he feared that sales would drop: other professional cyclists might think that the British team's failures were due to the quality of the bikes. Brailsford was tasked with taking British cycling to a new level was loaded. Brailsford and his team began with small changes to help the national team move closer to professional team status. They redesigned the saddle to make the bikes

more comfortable and began rubbing alcohol on the tires to improve traction. They asked the cyclists to wear electric jackets. Along the way, the coach continued to fix small things that no one noticed, in order not to stop observing and providing comfort.

The coach is not even a member of the group

They also involve a surgeon in how to reduce the level of pollution, how to clean their hands. They also try different pillows and mattresses to improve the quality of their sleep. It's harder to see the dust in the cars, the athletes used to not be upset by seeing the dust and always cleaned the car. Such and such small corrections lead to the expected result. "

The writer herewith alludes to every small change and comfort that we don't notice to lead us to greatness.

The president of our country Sh.Mirziyoyev issued many decisions about a satisfactory approach to education. In order to make education effective, qualified psychologists, English language teachers, and similar specialists were employed in preschool and primary classes. In order to improve the quality of education, our state has provided sufficient funds and facilities such as textbooks.

In particular, due to the pandemic, the quarantine of higher education institutions and schools has been established. Despite this, many facilities have been created by our state.

For example: A special tariff plan "Education" has been introduced for the use of mobile communication services under favorable conditions for teachers and trainers in distance education. Currently, more conveniences are included in this tariff plan. It should be mentioned here that from the beginning of the year until today, more than 9,000 kilometers of optical fiber communication lines have been built in order to expand the possibilities of broadband connection to the Internet. The main part of the built optical fiber communication lines was organized for the objects of the social sphere. It is noted in the message that the introduction of distance education into the higher education system will help to reduce educational costs for both the state and the student. This, in turn, serves to increase admission quotas.

Also from the workplace of students

their continuous education is also important in ensuring the harmony of two activities - education and labor activities.

Currently, about 250,000 children with various disabilities (under 16 years of age) need education in Uzbekistan. It is necessary to organize special services for disabled children together with education. 86 special educational and mixed special institutions, 982 special kindergartens for blind, deaf and hearing-impaired children, poliomyelitis patients, mentally retarded children, speech-impaired and mute children there is. There are a number of such facilities and opportunities, and it is in the hands of us young personnel and the future generation to use them properly.

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